

Sustainable Claims, Unsustainable Realities: Qualitative Insights into Greenwashing in Ecotourism Enterprises of Assam

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Abstract

In Assam, ecotourism has become a major sustainable alternative for the tourism industry. Sustainable development in ecotourism promotes conservation and community livelihood while minimising environmental consequences and maximising socio-cultural advantages. However, in addition to the sincere motive and rapid development of ecotourism, another significant idea known as "greenwashing" has emerged. It is a tactic used by businesses to erroneously or dishonestly claim environmental responsibility in order to draw eco-aware tourists and reap benefits. These claims cast doubt on the legitimacy of ecotourism in locations endowed by nature. Thus, this study explores the idea of "greenwashing" in ecotourism, how common it is in Assam ecotourism, and how tourists, operators, and residents perceive these tactics. Data for the qualitative study design was gathered through semi-structured interviews with tourists, ecotourism operators, and local community leaders, as well as a content analysis of marketing materials. Using NVIVO software, the thematic analysis offers various general themes. The study will offer policy recommendations to raise tourists' awareness of greenwashing and build operators' capacity to promote genuine, transparent, and sustainable ecotourism in Assam by reducing the impact of greenwashing.

Keywords

Ecotourism, Sustainable Development, Greenwashing, Authentic, Environment.

Introduction

Typically, the economic outcomes of the tourism sector and regional growth indicators, like employment generation, footfall of inbound tourists and outbound tourists, and demand creation, have historically been used to assess the industry's success (Koh et al., 2022; Fakfare and Wattanacharoensil, 2023). Subsequently, with the emergence of a green economy and rising consumer awareness of sustainability, green marketing has become an essential tool for businesses in a variety of industries, including tourism, to obtain a competitive edge in the market (Moravcikova et al., 2017; Lu et al., 2021). The process of reducing a product's environmental impact through redesign, sustainable production, and well-coordinated marketing methods is known as "green marketing." Its goal is to support items that are environmentally friendly and meet the rising demand for sustainable consumption (Dahhan & Arenkov, 2021).

Despite the fact that tourism professionals generally view ecotourism as beneficial (Fakfare and Wattanacharoensil, 2023) various negative externalities surrounding this industry have been brought to light, including overcrowding in traditional destinations (World Travel and Tourism Council, 2021), excessive energy consumption (Shakouri et al., 2017), or the emission of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere (Mishra et al., 2022). This is demonstrated by the fact that between 2009 and 2013, tourism accounted for 8% of global greenhouse gas emissions (Lenzen et al., 2018). Accordingly, encouraging responsible traveller behaviour is a significant challenge for the tourism industry (Turaga et al., 2010). There is a report by the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the Tourism Council (WTTC), and the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC, 2021) that in 2019, tourism contributed 5.4 billion tonnes of CO₂ emissions (WTTC, 2021). Greenwashing, which weakens sustainability's true essence and uses it as a commercial tagline, has not only affected consumer behaviour but also penetrated the tourism sector. Greenwashing in the travel and

tourism sector can take the form of ambiguous eco-labels, selective disclosure of sustainable initiatives, or overstatement of community involvement. This brings up important questions: Are the sustainability promises made by Assam's ecotourism industry genuine, or are they merely promotional tricks to draw in ecofriendly and environmentally conscious tourists?

In order to investigate greenwashing in Assam's ecotourism industry, this study seeks to understand how sustainability claims are formulated, how stakeholders and visitors view them, and what effects these actions have on the authenticity of ecotourism in the area.

Objective of study

This study has been undertaken to fulfill the following objectives:

1. To explore the concept of greenwashing in ecotourism.
2. To find out greenwashing in ecotourism in Assam from the perspectives of visitors, operators, and local communities.

Research Questions:

The study has the following research questions:

1. What is the concept of greenwashing in ecotourism?
2. How greenwashing is prevalent in ecotourism in Assam, and how visitors, operators and locals view these techniques?

Review of Literature

According to a study by Boo et al. (2009), ecotourism views a destination as if it were a product, evaluating its attributes based on both subjective and convincing premises. However, marketing a destination is quite different from marketing a consumer product. First of all, an ecotourism destination is a collection of many tourist amenities and is far more diverse than a simple commodity (Morgan et al., 2002). Research shows that consumers today believe the world is a small place with more opportunities for travel than at any previous point in the past (Morgan et al., 2002). Because of this, it is essential to lead effective promotion to draw attention to your destination in a highly competitive marketplace. Thus, fostering customer loyalty is one of destination advertisers' primary functions. The financial impact of ecotourism and growing competition make displaying destinations enticing. Branding a tourist site as a marketable commodity is a relatively new concept (Murphy et al., 2007). In Assam, Gogoi and Borah (2011) reported that both local and foreign tourists prefer Kaziranga National Park (KNP) because of its abundant bio-diversity resources. However, because ecotourism promotes community involvement, reduces pollution, and lessens human-animal conflict, it has been prioritised in Kaziranga (Baruah, 2010 and Khound 2011). In Assam, ecotourism draws a lot of people who enjoy the outdoors and animals, who want to experience vibrant wildlife in its natural environment. For example, Kaziranga has long had a consistent stream of nature tourists. More and more places, such as Manas, are being promoted as top locations for nature hikes and bird watching. However, in order to take advantage of this new trend, it is necessary to expand the ecotourism industry to include destinations other than the well-known animal sanctuaries and to employ innovative tactics (Bordoloi et al., 2012). While TerraChoice defines greenwashing as "the act of misleading consumers about a company's environmental practices or environmental performance and positive communication about environmental performance," Greenpeace defines it as "a public relations tactic used to make a company or product appear environmentally friendly without significantly reducing its environmental impact" (Greenpeace, 2021).

As businesses respond more and more to the demand for sustainability, the practice of "greenwashing" has grown to be a significant concern (Li et al., 2023; Sajid and Ertz, 2024). Among other things, the objective is to boost product value, boost popularity, adapt to market demands, test new markets, and win over customers with a positive image and social responsibility (Lintang, 2022).

Methodology

To acquire greater comprehension of the phenomenon of greenwashing in ecotourism in Assam, a qualitative exploratory design was used. To find out how tourists and operators and community stakeholders perceive about ecotourism and the existence of false sustainability claims, two focus groups were held. Ten ecotourism operators and lodge owners, five local community representatives involved in ecotourism activities, and fifteen visitors visiting Kaziranga National Park, Nameri National Park and Manas National Park, and specific eco-lodges were the three main stakeholder groups from whom data was gathered. FGDs also yielded firsthand insights into how ecotourism projects either adhere to or depart from true sustainability goals. The primary data is supplemented by a content analysis of promotional items, such as websites, brochures, and social media platforms. Data gathered through semi-structured interviews allow participants to share their thoughts and descriptive information

on the greenwashing in ecotourism (Farinloye et al., 2019). Qualitative analysis has been done by way of thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Data were coded, categorized, and analyzed to identify recurring themes.

Findings

Following a detailed analysis and discussion with co-authors and colleagues regarding the sub-themes and their ideal alignment with the major themes, the analysis produced a thematic table with 15 sub-themes (thematic analysis) and 5 main themes, as shown in Table No. 1.

Table 1: Thematic Analysis of Greenwashing in Ecotourism

Broad Theme	Sub-Theme	Descriptions
Marketing & Branding Practices	Misleading eco-labels	Use of “eco” in lodge/park branding, labelling and packaging
	Selective disclosure	Highlighting renewable energy use while concealing waste mismanagement.
	Overstated sustainability claims	Use of generic terms like “green,” “natural,” “environment,” or “eco-friendly” without practical evidence.
Operational Practices	Conservation	Planting a few trees or occasional clean-up drives as core sustainability initiatives, and conserving historic sites.
	Unsustainable resource use	High water consumption, poor waste segregation despite “eco” branding, using and disposing plastic bottles, cutlery etc.
	Energy Usage Contradictions	Solar panel promotion alongside diesel generator dependency
Tourist Perceptions	Confusion about eco-standards	Uncertain view of Tourists on Genuine Vs Fake sustainability claims.
	Distrust	Feeling deceived when eco-lodges don't provide the environmentally beneficial activities that were promised.
	Symbolic vs. substantive practices	Acknowledgement of external methods (such as using bamboo straws) in contrast to the absence of systemic sustainability
Community Perspectives	Marginal involvement	Local communities are used for promotional imagery but excluded from the decision-making process.
	Cultural Commodification	Traditions promoted as “eco-cultural” attractions without benefit-sharing.
	Unequal Benefit Distribution	Operators make more profit than local stakeholders, despite sustainability claims.
Digital and Promotional Content	Green Aesthetics	Use of green colour themes, nature, and wildlife visuals to imply sustainability.
	Social media storytelling	Promoting only environmentally friendly activities and leaving out non-sustainable ones
	Lack of transparency	Non-disclosure of sustainability certifications, audits, or impact assessments.

Our findings are in line with the thematic analysis discussed in the preceding section which aimed to comprehend the idea of greenwashing in ecotourism. Following that, these themes are examined and supplemented by relevant quotations from the participant reactions to the interview questions.

Marketing & Branding Practices

Participants shared their experiences and views on misleading eco-labels, selective disclosure, and overstated sustainability claims-

Tourist 1 (Kaziranga National Park): "The eco-lodge insisted on referring to itself as green, but they had no certification when I enquired about it. The label seemed to be purely decorative."

Tourist 6 (Manas National Park): "On site, they were still primarily using diesel generators, even though the website showcased their solar panels."

Operator 2: "Even though only a portion of our operations adhere to those standards, we market our property as eco-friendly because visitors expect it to be so."

Findings reveal that the branding of ecotourism services in Assam often relies on symbolic gestures rather than certified sustainability. The overuse of terms like eco, green, and sustainable without verifiable backing created suspicion among tourists. This indicates a form of "green glossing," where marketing narratives take precedence over operational realities. The mismatch between promotional claims and real-world practices undermines the trust and risks damaging the reliability of genuine initiatives of ecotourism.

Operational Practices

Tourist 2 (Kaziranga): "They emphasised water conservation, but I noticed plastic bottles all over the place and taps left open."

Community member 2: "They plant a few trees for photos and selfies, but the lodges don't support proper disposal, so our village still struggles with waste management."

Operator 3: "The primary purpose of the solar panels is marketing. In reality, the majority of power originates from conventional sources."

Therefore, it is seen that one of the main areas where greenwashing occurred was operational inconsistencies. Operators emphasised certain sustainability efforts, such solar panels or tree planting, but these were mostly symbolic and dominated by the constant reliance on unsustainable resource use, including diesel generators and inadequate waste management. Voices from the community reaffirmed that these activities are more symbolic than transformative. This illustrates the "practice-performance gap," wherein sustainability is implemented partially to satisfy visitor demands rather than completely integrated into operations.

Tourist Perceptions

Tourist 4: "Although I was thrilled to be staying in an eco-lodge, it felt exactly like a typical hotel—just some bamboo furniture and that's that."

Tourist 7: "It's challenging to determine whether location is truly environmentally friendly. I felt misled because everyone was using the same green phrases."

"The cultural dance and music were authentic," said the tourist 8 (Majuli), "but other things like noise and waste didn't feel sustainable at all."

Findings reveal that tourists were confused and disappointed by the inability to distinguish between genuine and fake eco-practices. Most of them felt misled by exaggerated claims and aesthetically pleasing modifications (such as bamboo furniture or cultural performances) marketed as environmentally beneficial experiences. This demonstrates how greenwashing undermines guests' trust in ecotourism branding, which may result in disillusionment and a decreased desire to return and repurchase and recommend. Furthermore, operators cannot continue to rely solely on symbolic practices due to tourists' increased understanding of sustainability, as they are becoming more adept at spotting anomalies.

Community Perspectives

Community member 1: "They promote our flora and fauna, handlooms and cultural dances, but we don't share in the benefits."

Community member 3: "Eco-tourism campaigns often feature us in images and videos, but we are rarely consulted."

Community leader: "Our people still struggle with basic facilities, while operators profit from ecotourism."

According to community narratives, the development of ecotourism was marginalised. Despite extensive marketing of regional culture and heritage, communities frequently lack access to decision-making processes and receive scant tangible benefits. The commodification of cultural authenticity as a sustainability symbol without fair benefit-sharing is a more serious kind of greenwashing. The results emphasise that, in the name of environmental

friendliness, ecotourism runs the risk of replicating exploitative power dynamics in the absence of true community participation.

Digital and Promotional Content

Tourist 10: "The location appeared so serene and green on Instagram, but when I actually arrived, construction and traffic noise disrupted my entire stay."

Tourist 12: "The rivers appeared clean in their Facebook posts, but there was plastic trash visible close to the lodge."

Operator 5: "We concentrate our social media on positive eco-images because that is what attracts customers."

Promotional materials have been found to be a major source of greenwashing, especially on social media. An idealised picture of eco-practices that frequently did not correspond with the realities on the ground was created by images of beautiful landscapes, green colour patterns, and controlled narratives. Although this "aesthetic greenwashing" works well to draw tourists, when their expectations are not fulfilled, it eventually makes them unhappy. The disparity between lived experience and digital narratives serves as an example of how marketing may skew sustainability messaging, highlighting the necessity of third-party verification and transparent reporting.

Conclusion

Finally, it can be said that through the viewpoints of travellers, tour operators, and Assamese local communities, this study explored the ways in which greenwashing occurs in ecotourism. The results show that even while ecotourism is marketed as a sustainable alternative for the environment and culture, many practices are still either superficially or selectively addressed. Authentic sustainability is undermined by marketing methods that frequently rely on eco-labels and symbolic gestures that cannot be verified.

To overcome these challenges, a multi-stakeholder strategy is needed. First and foremost, ecotourism operators need to incorporate sustainability holistically into their everyday operations and go beyond symbolic gestures. This involves community-driven conservation initiatives, ethical energy use, and transparent waste management. Third-party audits and certification should be used to support eco-claims and increase visitor confidence. Second, in order to monitor sustainability communication, penalise false claims, and encourage authentic eco-friendly behaviours, policymakers and tourism authorities must set up clear legal frameworks. Third, to guarantee that ecotourism produces inclusive benefits, local communities should be empowered through capacity-building initiatives, revenue-sharing schemes, and participatory planning. Last but not least, in order to set reasonable expectations for visitors, digital communication strategies must prioritise authenticity and transparency by highlighting both achievements and current challenges. By emphasising authenticity and accountability, ecotourism industry of Assam can improve the experience of visitors, boost its reputation, and make a significant contribution to the region's sustainable development.

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